

Strategies for Enhancing Rural Information Service Access in Lapai LGA, Niger State: A Survey-Based Study

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Abstract

This study examined strategies for bridging the digital divide and improving access to information services among rural residents in Lapai Local Government Area (LGA), Niger State, Nigeria. A quantitative survey design was adopted. A sample size of 384 respondents was determined using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) formula. Convenience sampling was employed to select respondents who were available and willing to participate in the study. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, and mean scores, with the aid of SPSS version 23. Of the 384 questionnaires distributed, 255 were returned and found usable, representing a 66% response rate. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach's alpha coefficients, with all constructs exceeding the 0.70 threshold, indicating acceptable internal consistency. The findings revealed that the level of access to information services among rural residents in Lapai LGA is generally low, particularly in relation to agricultural, health, educational, and government information services. Major barriers identified included poor internet connectivity, inadequate electricity supply, high costs of internet services and digital devices, low digital literacy, distance to information centres, language barriers, and inadequate government support for ICT infrastructure. The study further found that improving internet connectivity and electricity supply, establishing community ICT centres, providing digital literacy training, subsidizing internet services and digital devices, promoting local language content, and increasing government investment in ICT infrastructure were viable strategies for improving access to information services. The study concluded that bridging the digital divide in rural communities requires combined infrastructural, economic, educational, and policy interventions. It recommended increased government investment in rural ICT infrastructure, digital literacy training, subsidized internet services, and the establishment of community-based information centers to improve access to information services and promote socio-economic development in rural communities.

Keywords: Digital Divide, Information Services, Rural Communities, ICT Infrastructure, Lapai Local Government Area, Niger State.

Introduction

Access to reliable information services is essential for economic growth, educational development, healthcare awareness, effective governance, and overall societal progress. In recent years, digital technologies have transformed the way information is created, stored, disseminated, and accessed across the world. Through technologies such as the internet, mobile devices, digital libraries, and online information platforms, individuals can easily obtain and utilize information for education, agriculture, healthcare, governance, and entrepreneurship. Despite these advancements, significant disparities remain between urban and rural communities in terms of access to digital technologies and information services (Kuteesa et al., 2024; Salemink et al., 2017). This inequality is commonly referred to as the digital divide.

The digital divide refers to the gap between individuals and communities that have adequate access to digital technologies and those that do not (Ishmuradova, 2024; Sripathi et al., 2024). In developing countries such as Nigeria, the divide is more pronounced in rural areas where inadequate ICT infrastructure, unstable electricity supply, poor mobile network coverage, weak internet connectivity, limited access to digital devices, low digital literacy, low-income levels, and the high cost of internet services continue to hinder access to information services (Townsend et al., 2013; Omweri, 2024; Fadimatu et al., 2024). These challenges restrict access to online educational resources, healthcare information, agricultural innovations, employment opportunities, financial services, e-government services, and other vital information resources. Consequently, they widen socio-economic inequalities and slow rural development.

Lapai Local Government Area of Niger State is among the rural communities affected by inadequate access to information services. Many residents face difficulties in accessing reliable internet services, information centres, and digital communication tools (Djibo & Malam, 2024). The limited availability of ICT infrastructure and low levels of digital literacy further constrain access to information services. As a result, residents experience challenges in educational development, economic activities, healthcare awareness, agricultural productivity, communication, civic participation, and access to government services that are increasingly delivered through digital platforms.

Addressing the digital divide in Lapai LGA is therefore critical for promoting equitable access to information and enhancing socio-economic development. Strategies such as expanding internet infrastructure, improving electricity supply, subsidizing internet services and digital devices, establishing community digital canthers, strengthening digital literacy programs, supporting public libraries with ICT facilities, promoting local language content, and implementing supportive government policies have the potential to improve information access among rural populations. Understanding the extent of information access, the barriers faced by residents, and the strategies required to overcome these challenges is essential for effective intervention and policy formulation.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the growing importance of digital technologies in facilitating access to information and improving quality of life, many rural communities in Nigeria continue to experience limited access

to information services due to the persistent digital divide. In Lapai Local Government Area, many residents lack reliable internet connectivity, stable electricity supply, affordable digital devices, and the digital skills required to effectively utilize online information resources (Ahmad & Buba, 2025; Mishi & Anakpo, 2022). These limitations reduce their ability to access timely information for education, healthcare, agriculture, business, and socio-economic development (Mtega & Benard, 2013). Several studies in Nigeria have examined the digital divide and challenges of ICT access in rural communities. Within Niger State, existing studies have largely focused on ICT adoption, information access challenges, and the availability of communication infrastructure in selected communities and institutions (Nabaraa et al., 2023; Tanko et al., 2013). However, there is limited empirical evidence specifically addressing strategies for improving access to information services among rural residents in Lapai Local Government Area. Consequently, little is known about the unique barriers affecting information access in the area and the most appropriate interventions for addressing them. Although governments, telecommunication providers, and development agencies have implemented various initiatives aimed at reducing digital exclusion, access to information services among many rural residents remains inadequate. The absence of locality-specific evidence makes it difficult to design interventions that effectively respond to the realities of communities in Lapai LGA. This study therefore investigates the level of access to information services among rural residents in Lapai LGA, identifies the barriers limiting access, and examines strategies for bridging the digital divide and improving information access in the area.

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to examine strategies for bridging the digital divide and improving access to information services among rural residents in Lapai LGA, Niger State. The specific objectives are to:

1. Assess the current level of access to information services among rural residents in Lapai Local Government Area.
2. Identify the barriers affecting access to information services among rural residents in Lapai Local Government Area.
3. Examine strategies for improving access to information services among rural residents in Lapai Local Government Area.

Literature Review

Current Level of Access to Information Services among Rural Residents

Access to information services is widely recognized as essential for social inclusion, economic growth, education, and community empowerment. According to Musingafi and Zebron (2014), access to information services enables rural populations to improve productivity, reduce poverty, and participate effectively in socio-economic activities. However, many rural communities in Nigeria continue to experience inadequate access to modern information services due to infrastructural and socio-economic challenges (Garaba & Mohammed, 2019; Mtega, 2012). Research has further shown that only a small proportion of rural residents have reliable access to electricity, internet services, digital devices, and community information centers necessary for effective participation in the digital information environment (Okocha & Edafewotu, 2022). Existing studies consistently demonstrate that rural communities face greater challenges in

accessing digital information due to unstable electricity supply, poor internet connectivity, low awareness of available resources, low digital literacy, weak policy support, and inadequate ICT facilities required for digital access (Bello et al., 2016). Consequently, many rural residents have limited access to online education, healthcare information, e-government services, and digital economic opportunities.

Barriers Affecting Access to Information Services among Rural Residents

Numerous factors have been identified as barriers to information service access in rural communities. One of the most prominent challenges is inadequate infrastructure. Poor electricity supply, limited broadband connectivity, weak telecommunication networks, and insufficient ICT facilities significantly hinder access to digital information services (Vassilakopoulou, 2023; Paul & Eghe, 2023). Low digital literacy further limits the ability of rural residents to effectively utilize ICT tools and online services (Samuel-Okon & Abejide, 2024). Economic barriers, including the high cost of smartphones, computers, internet subscriptions, and data services, also restrict access among low-income households (Okocha & Edafewotu, 2022).

In addition, language and cultural barriers reduce information accessibility because much digital content is not available in local languages understood by rural populations (Sedoyeka, 2012). Inadequate government policies, insufficient investment in ICT infrastructure, and weak institutional support continue to hinder efforts to bridge the digital divide (Sanders & Scanlon, 2021). These challenges collectively limit access to educational resources, healthcare services, government programs, financial services, and agricultural innovations delivered through digital platforms. Understanding these barriers is therefore essential for developing effective strategies to improve information access among rural residents in Lapai LGA.

Strategies for Improving Access to Information Services among Rural Residents

Several scholars have proposed strategies for improving access to information services and bridging the digital divide in rural communities. One of the most frequently recommended approaches is the improvement of ICT infrastructure through enhanced internet connectivity, stable electricity supply, and stronger telecommunications networks (Reddick et al., 2020). Researchers have also emphasized the need to subsidize internet services, data subscriptions, and digital devices to make them more affordable for rural populations (West, 2015; Lněnička & Máchová, 2022). Digital literacy training is another important strategy, as it equips rural residents with the knowledge and skills required to effectively use ICT tools and online platforms (Townsend et al., 2013). Similarly, the establishment of community ICT centers, public libraries, internet cafés, and digital learning hubs can provide affordable access points for individuals who cannot afford personal digital devices (Ochillo, 2022).

Furthermore, the development of local-language digital content and public awareness campaigns can improve the accessibility and usability of information services among rural populations (George, 2024). Providing information in indigenous languages enhances comprehension and encourages greater use of digital platforms, while awareness campaigns conducted through community outreach programs and local radio stations can increase understanding of the benefits of digital technologies. Strengthening policy support and securing adequate funding from

government and development partners are also critical to reducing the rural information access gap (Reddick et al., 2020).

These strategies are particularly relevant to Lapai Local Government Area, where many rural residents continue to face challenges related to poor ICT infrastructure, low digital literacy, and inadequate institutional support (Nemer, 2015). Implementing a combination of infrastructural, educational, economic, and policy interventions can significantly improve access to information services and contribute to sustainable rural development.

Methodology

This study adopted a quantitative research method using a survey design. The population consisted of rural residents in Lapai Local Government Area, Niger State, Nigeria. According to the National Population Commission (2006), the population of the area is 110,127. However, it should be noted that this figure is outdated, and more recent population projections were not available at the time of the study, which may limit the precision of population estimates. A sample size of 384 respondents was determined using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) formula. Convenience sampling was used to select respondents who were available and willing to participate in the study. This non-probability sampling technique was adopted due to accessibility challenges in reaching dispersed rural populations; however, it introduces sampling bias and limits the generalizability of the findings to the wider population.

Data were collected through a structured questionnaire divided into four sections. Section A contained 4 items on demographic information, Section B had 5 items on the level of access to information services, Section C contained 10 items on challenges affecting access to information services, while Section D included 10 items on strategies for improving access to information services. Responses were measured using a four-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (4) to Strongly Disagree (1). The instrument was adapted from previous studies (Okocha & Edafewotu, 2022) and validated by experts in Library and Information Science to ensure face and content validity. Reliability was tested using Cronbach's alpha, with all constructs exceeding the acceptable threshold of 0.70: level of access (0.87), challenges (0.75), and improvement strategies (0.79).

Out of the 384 questionnaires distributed, 255 were returned and found usable, representing a 66% response rate. The lower-than-expected response rate reduces the effective sample size and may affect representativeness of the findings, particularly in a rural and heterogeneous population such as Lapai LGA. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23 through descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, and mean scores. A benchmark mean of 2.50 was used for decision making, where items with mean scores of 2.50 and above were accepted, while those below 2.50 were rejected.

Results and Discussion

Respondents' Demographic Information

Table 1: Respondent Demographic Information

Table with 4 columns: Variable, Categories, Frequency, Percentage. Rows include Gender, Age, Education Level, and Occupation with their respective counts and percentages.

Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of the respondents. Of the 255 respondents, 210 (82%) were male and 45 (18%) were female. Regarding age, 114 (45%) were between 18 and 30 years, 96 (38%) were between 31 and 50 years, and 45 (17%) were above 50 years.

The results indicate that most respondents were male and within the economically active age group. The majority had primary or secondary education, while farming was the predominant occupation. This reflects the agrarian nature of the study area and suggests the importance of information services that support agriculture and rural development.

Table 2: Level of Access to Information Services Among Rural Residents in the Lapai LGA

Table with 7 columns: S/N, Item Statements, SA, A, D, SD, Mean. Rows describe access to information services, agricultural information, health-related information, and educational resources.

5	I have access to government-related information services	24 9.41%	41 16.08%	50 19.61%	140 54.90%	1.80
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Key: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 2 presents the level of access to information services among rural residents in Lapai LGA. The results show that access to information services was generally low, as all mean scores were below the benchmark of 2.50. Most respondents disagreed that they had access to general information services (75.29%, mean = 1.37), agricultural information (70.59%, mean = 1.47), health-related information (65.10%, mean = 1.57), educational resources (63.53%, mean = 1.63), and government-related information services.

The findings indicate limited access to essential information services in the study area. The low mean scores suggest inadequate availability of information needed for agriculture, health, education, and civic engagement. This supports the findings of Garaba and Mohammed (2019) who reported poor access to information services in many African rural communities due to infrastructural challenges. The situation may be linked to poor telecommunications, limited internet connectivity, unreliable electricity supply, and inadequate information dissemination channels. These findings highlight the need to improve information infrastructure and access to information services in rural areas.

Table 3: Barriers to Information Service Access Among Rural Residents in the Lapai LGA

S/N	Item Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Mean
1	Poor internet connectivity limits access to information services	195 76.47%	60 23.53%	0 0%	0 0%	3.76
2	Lack of electricity affects access to information services	218 85.49%	37 14.51%	0 0%	0 0%	3.86
3	High cost of internet services and digital devices limits my access to information	155 60.78%	90 35.29%	10 3.92%	0 0%	3.57
4	Lack of digital devices prevents access to information services	149 58.43%	96 37.65%	10 3.92%	0 0%	3.55
5	Lack of digital skills affects my ability to use information services	160 62.75%	91 35.69%	4 1.57%	0 0%	3.61
6	Low level of education affects the ability to use information services	150 58.82%	96 37.65%	9 3.53%	0 0%	3.55
7	Distance to libraries or information centers affects access to information services	125 49.02%	100 39.22%	30 11.76%	0 0%	3.37
8	Poor road network affects access to information centers	125 49.02%	108 42.35%	22 8.63%	0 0%	3.41
9	Language barriers affect understanding of available information services	120 47.06%	115 45.10%	20 7.84%	0 0%	3.39
10	Inadequate government support in ICT infrastructure affects access to information	135 52.94%	105 41.18%	15 5.88%	0 0%	3.47

Key: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 3 presents the barriers to information service access among rural residents in Lapai LGA. All identified barriers had mean scores above the benchmark of 2.50, indicating respondents' agreement that they hinder access to information services. Lack of electricity had the highest mean score (3.86), followed by poor internet connectivity (3.76), lack of digital skills (3.61), high costs of internet services and digital devices (3.57), lack of digital devices (3.55), low educational level (3.55), inadequate government support for ICT infrastructure (3.47), poor road networks (3.41), language barriers (3.39), and distance to libraries or information centers (3.37).

The findings show that infrastructural, economic, educational, and institutional factors limit access to information services in the study area. Electricity and internet challenges emerged as the most significant barriers, highlighting the importance of digital infrastructure. These findings are consistent with previous studies (Samuel-Okon & Abejide, 2024; Reddick et al., 2020) which identified infrastructure, affordability, and digital literacy as key determinants of information access. The results suggest the need for improved infrastructure, affordable digital services, and capacity-building initiatives to enhance access to information services in rural communities.

Table 4: Strategies for Improving Access to Information Services in the Lapai LGA

Table with 7 columns: S/N, Item Statements, SA, A, D, SD, Mean. It lists 10 strategies for improving information access, such as providing free internet, improving telecommunication networks, and reducing internet costs, with corresponding response counts and percentages.

Key: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 4 presents respondents' views on strategies for improving access to information services in Lapai LGA. All proposed strategies recorded mean scores above the benchmark of 2.50, indicating agreement among respondents. Providing free or affordable internet services had the highest mean score (3.67), followed by improved electricity supply (3.66), digital literacy training (3.62), and better telecommunication networks (3.61). Other strategies included establishing community ICT centres (3.59), reducing internet costs (3.52), providing affordable digital devices (3.52), increasing government investment in ICT infrastructure (3.41), government-NGO collaboration (3.35), and providing information services in local languages (3.28).

The findings show strong support for strategies that address infrastructural and capacity-related challenges. Affordable internet access, reliable electricity, and improved telecommunication networks were identified as key measures for enhancing information access. These findings align with studies by Reddick et al. (2020) and West (2015), which emphasized the importance of infrastructure in reducing the digital divide. Respondents also highlighted the need for digital literacy programs, community ICT centers, government investment, partnerships with NGOs, and local-language information services. Overall, the results suggest that improving rural information access requires coordinated infrastructural, educational, economic, and policy interventions.

Conclusion

The digital divide continues to pose a serious challenge to effective access to information services in rural communities. This study examined strategies for improving access to information services among rural residents in Lapai Local Government Area, Niger State. The findings revealed that access to information services in the area is generally low due to a combination of infrastructural, economic, educational, and institutional barriers. Key constraints include poor internet connectivity, unstable electricity supply, high cost of digital devices and internet services, low levels of digital literacy, long distance to information centers, language barriers, and inadequate government support for ICT development. Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive approach. Respondents recommended a range of strategies such as improving internet connectivity, telecommunication networks, electricity supply, community ICT centers, and digital literacy training. Other important measures include reducing the cost of digital devices and internet services, providing information in local languages, and strengthening collaboration between government and NGOs.

This study contributes to the existing body of knowledge by providing valuable insights into the level of access to information services and the barriers faced by rural residents in Lapai LGA, thereby offering evidence to support policies and interventions aimed at bridging the digital divide. However, the findings should be interpreted with caution due to certain limitations, including the study's restriction to Lapai LGA, the use of convenience sampling, the lower-than-expected response rate of 66%, and reliance on outdated 2006 population data, all of which may affect the representativeness and generalizability of the results. Future studies should replicate this research in other local government areas and states in Nigeria to improve comparability and generalizability. Researchers should also employ probability sampling techniques, higher response rates, and use more recent population data to strengthen the reliability of findings.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study and the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are proposed to improve access to information services among rural residents in Lapai LGA:

1. The Niger State Government and relevant stakeholders should improve electricity supply, internet connectivity, and mobile network coverage in rural communities within Lapai LGA to enhance access to essential information services.
2. Community-based information canters equipped with computers and internet facilities should be established across rural communities in Lapai LGA to improve accessibility to digital and non-digital information resources.
3. Digital literacy programs should be organized regularly to equip rural residents with the skills needed to effectively use smartphones, computers, and online information platforms.
4. Government, NGOs, and telecommunication companies should subsidize the cost of internet services and digital devices to make information services more affordable and accessible to rural residents.
5. Digital information services should be made available in local languages commonly spoken in Lapai LGA. Government agencies and content developers should support the translation and localization of essential information relating to health, education, agriculture, and governance.
6. Information professionals and librarians should intensify outreach services by organizing information literacy campaigns, mobile library services, and community awareness programs to improve information access and utilization among rural residents.
7. Library associations such as the Nigerian Library Association (NLA) should collaborate with government agencies, NGOs, and community leaders to advocate for improved ICT infrastructure and rural information service delivery.
8. Academic institutions, especially departments of Library and Information Science, should partner with rural communities to provide training, research support, and community-based information services aimed at reducing information inequality and promoting digital inclusion.

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